

Scan me!

Semantic features of phraseological units of the English language denoting “time”

Munira Xakimova¹ [orcid: 0009-0005-4677-5279](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-4677-5279)

e-mail: munirakhakimova2575@gmail.com

*Senior teacher, Department of Foreign language and literature,
University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences, Gavhar Str. 1, Tashkent 100149, Uzbekistan*

Abstract: In this article we studied different specific features of phraseological units denoting “time” in the English language. While denoting with phraseological units denoting “time”, we can frequently find the lexeme “time” in the different position in the structure of phraseological units: e. g: before one’s time, time is money, have all the time in the world. While dealing with phraseological units denoting “time” we could find the lexeme “time” in different position in the structure of phraseological units. Besides that, many different proverbs, presumes, historical events, national regalia words can be found in the English language. Although phraseological units denoting “time” are frequently observed in the English language, to our mind, because of the member of this type phraseological units we tried to use above mentioned historical phraseological units to analyze more deeply the status of the phraseological units denoting time in the English Language.

Keywords: Proverb, unit, lexicons, discourse, metonymy, perception, influence, regalia, semantic, motivation.

1 Introduction

Teaching and learning of foreign languages specifically the English language has become one of the most important matters in our Republic after having achieved the state sovereignty in 1991-as the need for specialists with a good command of foreign languages is increased. The development of scientific researches is paid a special attention by the state government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the “National Program of Preparation of Specialists” adopted in 1997. A special stress is given to the development of the education system to a higher level, to improving national spirituality and outlook to the implementation of public schools properly with the necessary equipment and the advanced teaching technology in teaching process.[1]

The perfect language policy led by the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides the creation of all conditions that serve the stable development of languages of all nationalities existing in our country.[2]

The problem of phraseological units has always been one of the most disputable, interesting and important matters of general linguistics. A number of great linguists and lexicologists as such Vinogradov V, Arnold I, Smirnitkiy I, Koon in A and many others have deeply investigated the main peculiarities of phraseological units. Their investigations have served as the bases of our research work. Although the problem of phraseological units has been investigated by many linguists this matter still needs further investigation.

2 Methods

Lexicology is the part of linguistics dealing with the vocabulary of a language and the properties of words as the main units of language. The term lexicology is composed of two Greek morphemes: lexis meaning – “word, phrase” hence lexicons “having to do with words” and logos which denotes “a department of knowledge”. This, the literal meaning of the term lexicology is “the science of the word”. The term vocabulary is used to denote the system formed by the sum total of all the words that the language possesses. The term word denotes the basic unit of a given Language resulting from the association of particular meaning with a particular group of sounds capable of a particular grammatical employment. [3]

A word therefore is simultaneously a semantic, grammatical and phonological unit. The term word will be discussed at length later on: nevertheless recognized as proved by the existence of a sizable, literature of article, dissertations and book- length monographs. The distinction between the two basically different ways in which Language may be viewed the historical or diachronically- (Gr. die “through” and chromos “time”) and descriptive

or synchronic – (Gr. sync “together”, “with”) is a methodological distinction, a difference of approach, artificially separating for the purpose of study what in real Language is inseparable because actually every linguistic structure and system exists in a state of constant development. The distinction between a synchronic and a diachronic approach is due to the Swiss philologist Ferdinand de Saussure (1857-1913) [4]. The concept sphere of time is a dynamic process where the representation of time is influenced by human experience, common cultural background and society. The unanimous understanding and perception of time in English society is formed by the influence of Christian religion. For instance: Times a fifth of the God Time is god’s creature. In the process of existing English-American language Society under the influence of extra linguistic factors certain changes are undergone in the representation of time; the content structure of the concept time is modified with mental transformations. Conceptual metaphors are formed:

Time is recourse, time is a commodity. Time is money. By the influence of modern telecommunication and computer technological period new conceptual metaphors of time are appeared:

- Time is a virtual entity.

Main characteristics of temporality which is specific for the concept “time” are smoothness, orientation of relative watcher; continuity, duality of waters position, volume, dynamics, attention, substantiality, perfectness, discreteness.

Metonymical transference process also plays an essential reel in the conceptualization of time. Interaction of metaphor and metonymy can be found both in conceptual and language level.

3 Result

Based on modern tendency of the term concept we can define a concept as mental formation which owns such characteristics as universality/uniqueness, simplex / complexity, national/cultural specific feature that can be realized in different language levels. The concept “time” is a universal concept having identical semantic structure in English, Spanish, and Russian. This structure follows the nucleus - prophetic model which in the center is set meaning of continuity.

“Period of time”, “moment”, “circle” represent close periphery of the concept, “present”, “past”, “future” are sub concepts which form linear structural organization of time. Close periphery “human life” (age), “the life of nature” (a season). “Moment” may have the sub concepts “beginning”, and “end”. The analysis of potential seems of the word-term “time” and word-terms of sub concepts of time gives a chance to distinguish. For periphery of the concept formed by other concepts, which can be distinguished and as independent mental units: “youth”, “old age”, “birth”, “death”, “season”, “fast”, “and slow”.

Fundamental conceptual metaphors time is god’s creature, time is a gift of the god, forming Christian model of time find its reflection in the system of the English language and life in, the base of English-American language, world pictures.

The image of time-gift is not limited in religious discourse. It is characteristic for original English language texts, among which correspondence, poems, modern sociological and even in language works: “May God Bless her and you and grant you many years of peace and love”, “God speed you, ancient father, and give you a good day”, “... time was still understood as being God Given”, “One of our major cultural models of life is that each of us is allotted a certain fixed time on earth”.

The conceptual metaphor “time” is money lies on the base of understanding the time as money which is one of the types of material resource.

The time conceptualized as a resource and goods pretrial the characteristics of material object. Here the following conceptual metaphor is produced: Time is a solid object, where the happening event of time is understood as physical body. In lexical level to the notion of time the lexical semantic field of “shape” is produced: “Organization within a time – grid of calendars and clocks facilitating precisian”.

Thus, metonymy as well as metaphor plays an important role in the conceptualization of time which allows dividing the period of time with individual characteristics based on subjective perception of events and time as inseparable units.

The term motivation is used to denote the relationship existing between the morphemic, phonemic composition and structural pattern of the word on the one hand, its meaning on the other. There are three main types of motivation:[5]

1. Phonetical motivation
2. Morphological motivation
3. Semantic motivation

The derived word rethink is motivated in as much as its morphological structure suggests the idea of thinking again. Phonetically motivations are: - hiss, buzz, cuckoo, giggle, whistle. Its motivation is therefore morphological.

It is readily seen that motivation stops here on word level: the ultimate constituents, the morphemes re-and- think are non-motivated. Compare detainee, bituminize, etc. As to compounds, their motivation is morphological if the meaning of the whole is based on the literal meaning of the components, and semantic if the combination of components is used figuratively. Thus, eyewash as “a lotion for the eyes” is motivated morphologically. The same applies to such compounds as air-taxi, crash-Land, pressure-cabin, etc. If, on the other hand, eyewash is used metaphorically and means something said or done to deceive a person so that he thinks that what he sees is good, through in fact it is not; the motivation is semantic. Compare also: heart- breaking, time-server, and lick-spittle.

Semantic motivation is based on the co-existence of direct and figurative meaning, i.e. of the old sense and new within the same synchronous system. Mouth continues to denote a part of the human face, and at the same time it can mean metaphorically any opening or outlet: the mouth of river, for instance. Its direct meaning the word mouth is not motivated, so that semantic motivation is also only relative.

When the connection between the phonetically and morphological structure of the word and its meaning is conventional and there is no synchronously perceptible reason for the word having the has, the word is said to be non-motivated.

Let us analysis some more examples of phraseological units denoting time which can be divided into two groups- fully non-motivated and partially non-motivated phraseological units. So, let us see some fully non-motivated phraseological units below:

E.g. When Queen Anne was alive- Juda qadim zamonda.

This phraseological unit is fully non-motivated as we can see the meaning of this phrase me cannot have anything in common with the words queen, Anne, alive. Here we understand very long time ago.

Another example: Rome was not built in a day. In this example we cannot see a direct translation or interpretation of the whole sentence where the words Rome, built day do not have direct connection with the interpretation of the phrase me. The Last example which we are going to study is a very well-known expression frequently found in fairy-tales- one upon a time which the tales be.g.in with (Bir bor ekan, bir yo'q ekan). E.g. Once upon a time, in a very small country town, at a considerable distance from London, there lived a little man named Nathaniel Pip kin... (Dickens, “Pickwick Papers”, chi XVII). – Bir bor ekan, bir yo'q ekan.

The second semantic group of phraseological units, as we have above mentioned is phraseological units of partially non-motivated ones. Let us analyze some examples below. For instance, Father time (Vaqt oily hakam)- The phraseological unit which is partially non-motivated i.e. here we can understand the interpretation of the word “time” where as the Lexeme father has completely lost its lexical dictionary meaning. e.g. A benevolent- looking person, with a broad forehead adorned like that of father time by a single lock of snowy hair (H.Haggard, “Stella Fresenius”, chi V)

Serve one's time (Xizmat davrini yakuniga yetkazmoq). E.g. Having served his time in Indian army ha was free to come home and stay with a good pension. (W. Thackeray, “Vanity Fair” chi LVII). e.g. While these acts and deeds were in progress in and out of the office of Sampson Brass, Richard Swilled, being often left alone there in, be.g.an to find the time hang heavy on his hands (Ch. Dickens, “The Old Curiosity Shop”, chi LVII).

In no time (darhol, tezda). E. g. The Queen's argument was that if something wasn't done about it in less than no time, she'd have everybody executed all round (L. Carroll) “Alice in Wonder Land”, chi VIII.

Make up for lost time (yo'qotilgan paytni o'rmini to'ldirmoq) e.g. the ack-ack guns opened up. Whether they were big ones or the light caliber... the guns always sounded as if their crews had been asleep and had started too late and were trying to make up for lost time. (S.Heym, “The Crusaders”, book I, ch4).

The last example which we are going to present is the phraseological units take one's time which can be partially non-motivated. e.g. “Look, Alan” he said. “In a situation like this it's best to take sometime and think it out”. (D. Carter, “Tomorrow is with us” chi. XI).

Dealing with the analysis of semantic features of phraseological units denoting time we can observe different linguistic phenomena such as synonymy, antonym, polysemy, euphemism, irony, sayings, proverbs, metaphor, metonymy and many others.

In linguistics, semantic analysis is the process of relating syntactic structures, from the levels of phrases, clauses, sentences and paragraphs to the level of the writing as a whole, to their Language-independent meanings, removing features specific to particular linguistic and cultural contexts to the extent that such a project is possible. The element of idiom and figurative lexicology is the study of lexis or stock of words in a language. We will also use the word vocabulary interchangeably with lexis. Take note that lexis and vocabulary are non-count nouns, if you need to refer to two individual items, you should talk about lexical items or vocabulary items. You might also encounter the term lexicon, which can be used in a couple of ways, firstly it can be used as a more technical version of lexis, and many people use it synonymously with dictionary. As an example here we point the phraseological units in time and on time which are each other from stylistic point of view.

4 Discussion

Discussing the problem of English phraseological units denoting time it should be noted that they can also have a stylistic meaning as expressive means or stylistic devices which supply stylistic coloring of the phraseological units of this type. Stylistically use of phraseological units points out that they may be used ironically, metaphorically, metonymically or euphemistically. Now let us take the following phraseological unit “take one’s time” which can also be used ironically. e.g.: Pledge had sent the apprentice to fetch some journal- box packing from the store-room and the apprentice was taking his time about coming back. (A. Saxton, “The Great Midland”, p 1919). This type of phraseological units can be also used as hyperbola. e.g. : time after time twenty and twenty times; ten times, Doreen times. I’ve told him twenty and twenty times.

Another example: times out of number times without number. And he and she had agreed times without number that novelty was the salt of life, the essence of interest and drama (Y. Galsworthy, “The white monkey”, parts I, chi XIII).

Metaphorical use of the phraseological units denoting time can be seen in the following example: Golden time.

It was a golden time of my life; we were happy, healthy and wealthy.

In the semantic analysis of the phraseological units denoting time we can observe a number of Americanisms and colloquial use of phraseological units. Let us see the following examples:

All the time (Americanism)

Have a thin time (coll.)

Hire one’s time hire one’s own time (aimer)

It beats my time (aimer.)

No time swap knives (aimer coll.)

Sell time (aimer), on time (aimer)

Take time (aimer), make time (aimer.)

He is a business all the time.

5 Acknowledgment

The study of historical development of the English phraseological units has always been one of the most important and interesting problems of English phraseology. From historical point of view the phraseological units denoting “time” have been originated from different historical sources such as mythology, the Bible, national regalia and the works of many writers. To prove our words, let us take the following phraseological units connected with time:

- a) Phraseological units connected with the English regalia: When queen Anne was alive (very long ago)
- b) Phraseological units connected with the historical facts: When Adam delved and Eve span, since Adam was a boy (coll. Long ago);
- c) Phraseological units connected with belief: halcyon days (peaceful time)
- d) Phraseological units connected with sea: When one’s ship comes home;
- e) Phraseological units of Shake spear isms: Salad days (Antony and Cleopatra) (youth), at one fell swoop (immediately) (Macbeth);
- f) Phraseological units used by Chaucer: a nine day’s wonder (not very long time);
- g) Phraseological units created by J. Milton: fall on evil days (bad days have come);
- h) Phraseological units connected with the Bible: at the eleventh hour (at the last moment);
- i) Phrase logical units connected with mythology: the golden age (very good peaceful time), take time by the forelock (to use convenient time), fiddle while Rome is burning; the tortoise wins the race while her hare is sleeping;
- j) Phraseological units connected with the borrowings: appetite comes with eating (French); Rome was not built in a day (French) time is money (Americanism)

According to their structure the phraseological units denoting time may have the following types of patterns:

1) Adjective + noun

E.g. a rough time, close time, fine time, etc.

2) Verb + noun

E. g has a time, lose time, Kill time, save time etc.

3) Preposition + noun

E.g. on time, in time, by time, against time, at a time etc.

4) Adverb + noun

E.g. next time, last time. Etc

5) Indefinite pronoun + noun

E. g. All the time.

6) Preposition + adjective + noun

E.g. in good time, at the same time, at odd time etc.

7) Verb + adjective + noun

E. g. Have a rough time, have a thin time etc.

8) preposition+ pronoun + noun

E.g. at this time, at that time, at one's time etc.

9) Numeral + noun

E.g. ten times, nine times out of ten, etc.

10) Preposition + noun+ preposition + noun

E.g. from time to time

11) Verb + pronoun + prepositional phrase + noun

e. g. put somebody up to the time

12) Noun + verb

e. g. time flies, time will tell, etc.

Dealing with the structural patterns of phraseological units denoting time it is also necessary to point out the use of sayings and proverbs which are closely connected with the historical practice of a given nation. According to their structure proverbs and saying are usually a number of sayings and proverbs connected with time:

e. g. Time is money.

Lost time is never found again.

Make hay while the sun shines.

Time cures all things.

Time is the best healer.

Time and tide wait for roman.

Time works wonders.

6 Conclusion

Phraseology appeared in the domain of Lexicology and is undergoing the process of secreting as a separate branch of linguistics. The reason is clear- lexicology deals with words and their meanings, where as phraseology studies such collocations is different of words (phraseology isms, phraseological units, idioms), where the meaning of the whole collocations is different from the simple sum of literal meanings of the words, comprising a phraseological unit. In our research we have studied different specific feature of English phraseological units denoting "time". While dealing with phraseological units denoting "time" we could find the lexeme "time" in different position in the structure of phraseological units. Besides that, many different proverbs, presumes, historical events, national regalia words can be found in the English language. Although phraseological units denoting "time" are frequently observed in the English language, to our mind, because of the member of this type phraseological units we tried to use above mentioned historical phraseological units to analyze more deeply the status of the phraseological units denoting time in the English language.

In this article we have looked through different specific feature of English phraseological units denoting "time". While dealing with phraseological units denoting "time" we could find the lexeme "time" in different position in the structure of phraseological units. Besides that, many different proverbs, presumes, historical events, national regalia words can be found in the English language. Although phraseological units denoting "time" are frequently observed in the English language, to our mind, because of the member of this type phraseological units we tried to use above mentioned historical phraseological units to analyze more deeply the status of the phraseological units denoting time in the English language. The phraseological units denoting "time" are very often found in the English language. Syntactically this type of phraseological units can be:

a) Noun phraseology isms

b) Verb phraseology isms

c) Adjective phraseology isms

d) Prepositional phraseology isms

e) Adverb phraseology isms

According to their motivation English phraseological units denoting "time" can be divided into completely and partially non-motivated. Different semantic changes such as poly semi, synonymy, antonym, homonymy, metaphor, metonymy, euphemisms can be observed in semantic analysis of the given type of English phraseological units. Phraseological units denoting "time" can be observed in non-motivated proverbs and sayings which are equal to the phraseological units.

Thus semantic analysis of the phraseological units helps us to point of the main features of English phraseology.

Summarizing all above given, it is possible to draw a conclusion that the study of English phraseological units, specifically phraseological units denoting “time” plays an essential role among linguistic researches.

References

1. Karimov I. A. Jamiyatimiz mafkurasi xalqni-xalq, millatni-millat qilishga hizmat qilsin “Tafakkur “ jurnali bosh muharriri savollariga javob, T. 1998, №2, 3T.
2. Karimov I. A. Biz tan lagan yo'l-demokratik taraqqiyot, mafkuraviy dunyo bilan hamkorlik yo'li. “Mulkdor” gazetasi , Toshkent, 2003. 25-aprel.
3. Arnold I.V “ The English Word “ Moscow, 1986, p.9
4. F.de Saussure. “Course de Linguistique general “, Paris, 1949.
5. Pullmans, “The principles of Semantics” Glasgow. 1959 p86-90
6. I.V. Arnold “The English Word” Moscow 1973 p28.
7. Burchfield R.W. The English Language. Land. ,1985
8. Canon G. Historical Changes and English Word formation: New Vocabulary items. N.Y., 1986.
9. Ginsburg R.S. et al. A Course in Modern English Lexicology. M., 1979.
10. Halliday M.A.K. Language as Social Semiotics. Social Interpretation of Language and Meaning. Land. 1979.
11. Howard Ph. New words for Old. Land. 1980.
12. Khakimova Munira “Neologism as a result of the nomination process” 2021/4 jurnal Nauka i obrazovaniya segodnya №4 (63)2021, strp.51-52, Moscow 2021
13. Munira Khabibullayevna Khakimova “The correlation between language and culture” Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Vol.2 Special Issue № 20 strp.729-732, Izdatel OOO” Oriental Renaissance”